

Performance Comparison of S- and E-band Upgrades of a C+L-band System

André Souza
Nokia, Optical Networks
Carnaxide, Portugal
andre.souza@nokia.com

Nelson Costa
Nokia, Optical Networks
Carnaxide, Portugal
nelson.costa@nokia.com

João Pedro
Nokia, Optical Networks
Instituto de Telecomunicações, IST
joao.pedro@nokia.com

Abstract—The rapid growth of data traffic in modern telecommunication networks requires the development of advanced optical communication systems capable of delivering higher data rates and increased bandwidth. C+L-band systems provide reliable and efficient data transmission over long distances. However, the escalating demand for bandwidth-intensive applications and services push the limits of these systems, prompting the exploration of additional spectral bands to enhance network capacity. This work analyses two possible band upgrades to a C+L-band system: S- or E-band. The systems (with and without Raman amplification) are compared regarding optical performance, network capacity and transceiver count requirements.

Index Terms—multi-band, optical communications, networking

I. INTRODUCTION

Traditional optical wavelength-division multiplexing (WDM) systems that operate solely within the C-band are approaching the fundamental Shannon capacity limit. To further expand the bandwidth of current optical fiber transport networks, technologies such as space-division multiplexing (SDM) and multi-band transmission (MBT) have emerged as promising solutions [1]. While SDM techniques (such as multi-core or multi-mode fibers) can significantly increase capacity, they also require substantial capital expenditure (CAPEX) due to the need for new fiber deployments. A more cost-effective alternative is multi-fiber transmission, which leverages existing dark fibers. However, in scenarios where dark fibers are not available, deployment costs can be similarly prohibitive [2].

MBT offers a compelling alternative by extending the transmission spectrum beyond the C-band, as illustrated in Fig. 1a. This approach is particularly attractive in cases where fiber deployment is expensive or infeasible [3]. Commercial systems already exploit the L band, effectively doubling the capacity of C-band-only systems, and ongoing research is focused on further extending the bandwidth by integrating additional transmission bands. However, such expansion introduces challenges, including optical performance imbalances, higher component costs, and complexities in traffic survivability and protection [4]. Increased fiber attenuation, higher optical amplifier noise figures (NF), and power transfer due to stimulated Raman scattering (SRS) lead to performance disparities across bands [5]. Additionally, components designed for these new bands tend to be more costly and less efficient.

Among the potential candidates for MBT, the S-band is particularly promising because of its fiber characteristics similar to those of the C- and L- bands. Several studies have demonstrated the benefits of incorporating the S-band into C+L systems to enhance capacity [6], [7]. However, the expanded spectral footprint of an S+C+L-band system — exceeding 13 THz — intensifies SRS-induced power transfer between channels, posing significant challenges to service survivability and network management.

To address these issues, some researchers propose using the E-band instead of the S-band [8]. By introducing a 14-THz guard band between the C+L and E bands, wavelength interdependencies can be reduced, simplifying network operations. This approach, while forgoing some spectral regions with the lowest fiber attenuation and limiting the use of Raman amplification in the C and L bands, offers potential advantages in operational stability and manageability [9].

In this study, we use numerical simulations to explore the advantages of enhancing a C+L-band optical system by incorporating the E-band, instead of the S-band, or by implementing Raman amplification. Building upon the findings in [9], we assess network performance with and without Raman amplification of C+L-, S+C+L- and E+C+L-band systems, offering new perspectives on optimizing spectral efficiency (SE) and improving the resilience of next-generation optical networks.

II. SIMULATION SETUP

We assume each amplification band spans 6 THz (as shown in Fig. 1b) and 120-GBd signals are transmitted within a 150-GHz spectral grid, resulting in 40 channels per band. We evaluate three MBT systems: C+L, S+C+L, and E+C+L. Each system can utilize up to 20 backward Raman pumps spaced by 1 THz. For the C+L-band system, Raman pumps are placed within the 199 THz to 218 THz range, while for the S+C+L-band system, they are placed between 205 THz and 224 THz. In the E+C+L-band system, all twenty Raman pumps are positioned between 219 THz and 238 THz, with none placed in the spectral gap between the C+L and E-bands to avoid E-band power depletion. This configuration follows the findings of [9], which demonstrated that placing pumps in this intermediate region results in suboptimal system performance.

Optical fibers are characterized by a dispersion parameter of 16.7 ps/nm/km @ 1550 nm and a dispersion slope of 0.058

Fig. 1. (a) Frequency-dependent fiber loss and nonlinear coefficient, (b) frequency bounds of each amplification band used in this work, and (c) Telefónica national reference network topology.

ps/nm²/km. Additionally, the frequency-dependent loss and nonlinear coefficient of this fiber type are shown in Fig. 1a. We consider the normalized Raman gain profile of [10] to calculate the stimulated Raman scattering (SRS) effect. Additionally, input and output connector losses of 0.25 dB and splice losses of 0.01 dB/km are assumed. After each fiber span, a band demultiplexer (with a 1 dB insertion loss) separates the transmitted bands and delivers them to the respective optical amplifier. We consider a band demultiplexer based on a band filter and assume its insertion loss will be slightly higher than current commercial C+L-band filters [11]. The lumped optical amplifiers are modeled by a constant noise figure of [6, 6, 7, 7] dB for the L-, C-, S-, and E-bands for gain values higher than 20 dB. For gain values smaller than 14 dB, the amplifiers' NF is assumed to be 2 dB higher. The NF is linearly interpolated for gain values ranging between 14 and 20 dB. Power losses are assumed to be perfectly compensated in each fiber span (considering the impact of the SRS effect and the gain provided by the Raman amplifiers). Additional system parameters are: transceiver OSNR of 38 dB, add/express OSNR of 38 dB/37 dB and a 0.05 dB GSNR penalty per in-line amplifier.

A. Power Optimization

Effective optimization of launch power and Raman pump settings is essential for maximizing the performance, specially in MBT systems due to the frequency-dependent behavior of component characteristics and the impact of SRS. To assess transmission quality, we compute the Generalized Signal-to-Noise Ratio (GSNR) for each transmitted channel. The nonlinear interference component of the GSNR is estimated using the Generalized Gaussian Noise (GGN) model, as implemented in GNPY, which numerically solves the GGN integrals via the composite trapezoidal rule. SRS effects are evaluated by numerically solving the Raman equations (both algorithms are available in the open-source Python library GNPY [12]).

We employ a multi-objective genetic algorithm to jointly optimize the launch power and design of the Raman amplifier [10] in a single-span configuration ($L_S = 70$ km). The

Fig. 2. Final optimal non-dominated solutions for the various transmission systems obtained after the convergence of the multi-objective optimization algorithm.

algorithm targets two simultaneous objectives: maximizing the ideal capacity of the single-span system and minimizing the total GSNR variation across bands. The ideal capacity is calculated as the sum of the capacities of all transmitted channels, where the capacity of channel i is given by $2 \cdot R_S \cdot \log_2(1 + \text{GSNR}_i)$, with R_S representing the symbol rate [13].

B. Network Simulations

To estimate the network capacity of each transmission system, we perform simulations using the Spanish national reference network (Fig. 1c), as published by Telefónica in [14]. For simplicity, all network spans are assumed to be 70 km in length.

A basic sequential routing and wavelength assignment algorithm is employed. Traffic demands follow the pattern described in [14], with payloads uniformly distributed between 200 and 800 Gbps. The algorithm first attempts to groom new connection requests into existing channels with the same source and destination, provided there is sufficient spare capacity. If grooming is not possible, the demand is routed along its

TABLE I
PER-BAND AVERAGE AND VARIATION OF THE GSNR [IN DB] FOR TRANSMISSION IN ONE 70-KM SPAN FOR THE OPTIMIZED SOLUTIONS WITH $\Delta\text{GSNR} = 0.5$ dB.

	C+L	C+L w/ Raman	S+C+L	S+C+L w/ Raman	E+C+L	E+C+L w/ Raman
L	23.6 ± 0.6	32.5 ± 0.4	23.7 ± 1.0	28.8 ± 0.5	23.6 ± 0.6	28.2 ± 0.3
C	25.2 ± 0.5	30.4 ± 0.9	22.9 ± 0.2	30.7 ± 0.2	25.2 ± 0.5	27.4 ± 0.5
S	-	-	24.5 ± 0.4	27.7 ± 0.8	-	-
E	-	-	-	-	20.1 ± 0.3	28.2 ± 0.9

shortest path, selecting the modulation format that minimizes the number of required lightpaths while remaining feasible. Among the available and optically feasible spectrum slots, the one with the smallest positive residual margin is chosen to reserve higher-quality slots for more demanding connections.

Five modulation formats are considered, ranging from 400 Gbps to 800 Gbps in 100 Gbps increments, based on [10]. A modulation format is deemed feasible if its required SNR is below the GSNR. If no valid combination of route, modulation format, and spectrum slot is found, the connection is blocked and the algorithm proceeds to the next request.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 2 presents the non-dominated solutions computed by the optimization algorithm. When examining the capacity values for solutions with an average $\Delta\text{GSNR}^b = 0.5$ dB, the baseline C+L-band system is the least favorable in terms of total ideal capacity due to the smaller number of channels and the absence of Raman pumps.

We start by analyzing three upgrade paths for the C+L-band system: incorporating Raman amplification, adding the S-band, and adding the E-band. Among these, the C+L-band system with Raman amplification yields the smallest capacity gain, offering a 29% increase over the baseline. The E+C+L-band configuration follows, achieving a 37% improvement. The highest capacity gain is observed with the S+C+L-band system (without Raman amplification), which delivers a 47% increase compared to the baseline.

Although Raman amplification is likely the most cost-effective upgrade, it yields the smallest capacity improvement. The E-band upgrade is generally less disruptive due to the 14 THz guard band between the C- and E-bands. Still, having a higher capacity than the C+L-band system with Raman amplification requires additional band filters at amplification stages and more interfaces, which increases overall cost. On the other hand, the S-band upgrade offers the highest capacity gain and may cost roughly the same as the E-band upgrade. However, it also expands the contiguous transmission bandwidth, which can complicate network management and exacerbate power transients in the event of link failures.

We then compare the optimized performance of systems incorporating Raman amplification. The S+C+L-band+Raman configuration delivers the highest total capacity, with a 39.5% increase over the C+L-band+Raman baseline whereas the E+C+L-band+Raman system offers a 32.8% capacity gain relative to the same reference. Notably, the capacity advantage

Fig. 3. Number of lightpaths with a given maximum bitrate averaged over all transmission channels for different transmission systems for the optimized solutions with $\Delta\text{GSNR} = 0.5$ dB.

TABLE II
NETWORK-WIDE AVERAGE SYSTEM CAPACITY FOR THE DIFFERENT TRANSMISSION SYSTEMS.

System	C+L	C+L w/ Raman	S+C+L	S+C+L w/ Raman	E+C+L	E+C+L w/ Raman
Capacity [Tb/s]	48	64	68	93	60	90

of the S+C+L-band system over the E+C+L-band system is around 6% with or without Raman amplification.

Table I presents the average and variation of GSNR per band after a single 70-km span. These values serve as the basis for estimating the GSNR of each channel at the end of its lightpath. Figure 3 illustrates the average number of lightpaths operating at maximum data rate across all channels for each transmission scheme. Although the network contains 435 shortest paths (calculated as $\frac{N_n \cdot (N_n - 1)}{2}$, with N_n equal to the number of nodes of the network, i.e., 30), the E+C+L-band system without Raman amplification cannot reach this number due to some channels being infeasible (insufficient GSNR).

Among the evaluated systems, the C+L-band configuration — with and without Raman amplification — demonstrates the highest spectral efficiency. This is attributed to the higher number of lightpaths using higher bitrates. This result therefore confirms that using additional bands with less favorable fiber and amplifier characteristics negatively impacts the spectral efficiency.

Table II presents the network-wide average capacity for the Telefónica network [15]. Compared to the single-span results in Fig. 2, band upgrades without Raman amplification yield

Fig. 4. Blocking probabilities for different total deployed loads for the optimized solutions with $\Delta\text{GSNR} = 0.5$ dB.

Fig. 5. Number of required interfaces for different total deployed loads for the optimized solutions with $\Delta\text{GSNR} = 0.5$ dB.

smaller capacity gains at the network level. For instance, adding the E-band increases average capacity by only 25% over the baseline (significantly less than the 37% gain observed in the single-span ideal capacity). In contrast, the S-band upgrade results in a 42% increase in network-wide average capacity.

Interestingly, enhancing the C+L-band system with Raman amplification leads to a 33% capacity improvement (higher than that achieved by adding the E-band without Raman). This outcome highlights the reduction in spectral efficiency resulting from integrating the S- or E-band into the C+L-band system. As a result, while additional bands increase the number of available channels, their benefit diminish over longer paths (i.e., multiple-span links), where spectral efficiency plays a more critical role.

We conclude by running network-wide simulations across the Telefónica topology for various offered traffic loads and transmission system configurations. Figure 4 shows the evolution of the blocking probability, while Fig. 5 illustrates the number of required interfaces (transceivers) as a function of

the deployed network load.

Among the Raman-amplified systems, the S+C+L-band configuration supports the highest load at a blocking probability of 10^{-2} , followed by the E+C+L-band and the C+L-band systems. Despite the reduced spectral efficiency introduced by additional bands, the S+C+L and E+C+L systems enable 61% and 78% higher network loads, respectively, compared to the C+L+Raman system, even though they offer only 50% higher transmission channels. The C+L-band system offers higher spectral efficiency, resulting in a slightly lower number of required interfaces. This advantage would become more significant if higher-order modulation formats (beyond 800 Gbps per channel) were considered, as most lightpaths in the C+L+Raman system already support 800 Gbps (see Fig. 3). Nevertheless, it should be noted that in a network with longer paths, this is unlikely to occur, since the lower spectral efficiency of S+C+L- and E+C+L-band systems will result in more pronounced shares of lower capacity formats, eventually resulting in the need to deploy more interfaces. At lower traffic loads, the difference in interface requirements is minimal due to limited grooming, influenced by the distribution of demand rates and underutilization of higher-rate lightpaths. However, as network load increases, grooming becomes more effective, and the interface savings become more evident. For instance, at a deployed load of 50 Tb/s, the C+L-band system with Raman amplification requires 1.8% and 2.1% fewer interfaces compared to the S+C+L- and E+C+L-band systems with Raman amplification, respectively.

Finally, we evaluate three upgrade strategies for the C+L-band system: incorporating Raman amplification, expanding to the S-band, and expanding to the E-band. The trends in total deployed capacity for blocking probabilities between $2 \cdot 10^{-2}$ and $6 \cdot 10^{-2}$ are consistent with those shown in Table II. At higher blocking probabilities (corresponding to heavier network loads) systems with more bands tend to support greater capacity. This is likely due to the increased number of available channels, which alleviates the spectral continuity constraint by making it easier to find contiguous frequency slots for lightpaths. However, at lower blocking probabilities (below $2 \cdot 10^{-2}$) and lighter network loads, spectral continuity becomes less of a limiting factor. In this regime, the C+L+Raman system achieves the highest deployed capacity, despite having the lowest ideal single-span capacity among the three upgrade options. This is attributed to its superior spectral efficiency, which becomes more critical than spectral continuity under lighter loads. The number of required interfaces further reflects the spectral efficiency of each system: the C+L+Raman configuration requires the fewest interfaces, followed by C+L, S+C+L, and E+C+L.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This study evaluated several upgrade strategies for enhancing the capacity of C+L-band optical transmission systems, including the addition of Raman amplification, and the extension to the S-band or E-band. Comparative analysis with multi-band configurations incorporating Raman amplification —

specifically S+C+L and E+C+L systems - revealed that Raman amplification plays a vital role in maintaining high spectral efficiency, particularly in large-scale network deployments. While the E+C+L-band system offers operational simplicity due to the guard band between the E- and C+L-bands, it achieves slightly lower total capacity than the S+C+L-band system. These findings highlight the trade-offs between capacity, spectral efficiency, and operational complexity when selecting an upgrade path for future optical networks.

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